

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring
data into the Digital Twin Ocean

D6.1 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DC&E) Strategy and Plan

20.12.2023

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Project Title	Integration of biodiversity monitoring data into the Digital Twin Ocean
Project Acronym	DTO-BioFlow
Project Number	101112823
Type of project	IA – Innovation Action
Topics	HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01-07
Starting date of Project	01 September 2023
Duration of the project	42 months
Website	https://dto-bioflow.eu/

D6.1 – Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DC&E) Strategy and Plan

Work Package	WP6 Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder outreach
Task	T6.1 Outreach, Communication, & Dissemination
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Version	V1.0
Due Date	31/12/2023
Submission Date	21/12/2023

Dissemination Level

x	PU: Public
	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)
	EU-RES. Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
	EU-CON. Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	30/11/2023	Rita Meneses & Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT)	ToC definition
0.2	05/12/2023	Rita Meneses, Fabiana de Carlo, Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT)	First draft
0.3	11/12/2023	Oonagh McMeel (SSBE), Lise Cronne-Grigorov (ICES), Christina Pavloudi (EMBRC-ERIC), Lynn Delgat, Leen Vandepitte (VLIZ)	Contributions from partners
0.4	13/12/2023	Rita Meneses, Fabiana de Carlo, Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT)	Final version for internal review
0.5	14/12/2023	Klaas Deneudt, Carlota Muñiz, VLIZ	Internal review
1.0	19/12/2023	Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT)	Final version

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
ARMS	Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures
DC&E	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation
DTO	Digital Twin Ocean
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
MBON	Marine Biodiversity Observation Network
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
SG	Stakeholder Group
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-Bound
ToC	Table of Content
WISE	Water Information System for Europe
WP	Work Package

Keywords

Digital Twin Ocean, Biodiversity data, Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation

Disclaimer

The DTO-BioFlow project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101112823. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Marine habitats present specific and one-of-a-kind issues when it comes to observing, mapping, and monitoring biodiversity in marine ecosystems. In spite of the fact that significant advancement has been made in Europe to collect, harmonise, and make available data on marine biodiversity, particularly as a result of the efforts of European research infrastructures (such as EMODnet, Copernicus Marine, and other related European and international initiatives (MBON - Marine Biodiversity Observation Network, OBIS - Ocean Biodiversity Information System, GOOS - Global Ocean Observing System), a large portion of the data that is currently being collected is unavailable and inaccessible; this type of data is referred to as "sleeping data". Funded through the EC Horizon Europe Programme and coordinated by the Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ), the DTO-BioFlow project aims to incorporate previously unavailable or difficult-to-access marine-biodiversity data into the biodiversity component of the EU Digital Twin Ocean, ensuring sustainable data flows for marine biodiversity research.

Over the next four years, the DTO-Bioflow consortium will work on consolidating standards, quality control, communication protocols, harmonisation pipelines, data products, data models, ingestion procedures and incentives for sustainable connection to improve the interoperability and digitisation of biodiversity data. The project will also test out various technologies that are both affordable and adaptable to carry out species monitoring on a large scale. The end-to-end approach will be demonstrated via a number of science-based policy-relevant use cases and via mechanisms to monitor, measure progress and drive community action towards increasing biodiversity data flows.

This deliverable presents the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DC&E) Strategy and Plan for the Project, organised around a series of four campaigns to ensure outreach, knowledge transfer, participation and capacity building amongst key target audiences. The document starts by introducing the objectives of the communication, dissemination and outreach activities and the target audiences. Each of the four campaigns are then described in detail, namely:

- Campaign #1, 'DTO-BioFlow project communication', aimed at ensuring wide promotion of the project and its results to key target audiences via sound digital communications (website, social media presence, materials & digital marketing actions);
- Campaign #2, 'Biodiversity Providers Onboarding' aimed at building durable relationships with DTO data providers via onboarding mechanisms including open calls for data providers, capacity building resources, training and workshops;
- Campaign #3, 'User uptake of DTO-BioFlow Outputs', aimed at promoting the uptake of DTO-BioFlow assets', through the development of users stories, communication, matchmaking events and workshops with users.
- Campaign #4, 'International community building in support of the Mission & UN Decade of Ocean Science' through strengthening knowledge exchange and professional relations amongst key stakeholder groups and international communities via the organisation and roll-out of workshops, networking and consultation activities, to define targets and commitments to increase the flow of biodiversity data into the DTO by 2030 and in support of the UN Decade of Ocean Science.

Finally, a chapter of the deliverable is also dedicated to how the project will monitor the impact, and consider the exploitation of the project results beyond the consortium boundaries.

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1. Introduction

Marine habitats present specific and one-of-a-kind issues when it comes to observing, mapping, and monitoring biodiversity in marine ecosystems. In spite of the fact that significant advancement has been made in Europe to collect, harmonise, and make available data on marine biodiversity a large portion of the data that is currently being collected is unavailable and inaccessible. The core mission of the DTO-BioFlow Project is to unlock these “sleeping” biodiversity data enabling sustained flows of these, and new data, via primary integrators such as EMODnet into the EU Digital Twin Ocean. It will create a digital replica of marine biological processes transforming new and existing data flows into environments supporting the development of evidence-based knowledge.

Over the next four years the DTO-BioFlow consortium will work on consolidating standards, quality control, communication protocols, harmonisation pipelines, data products, data models, ingestion procedures and incentives for sustainable connection, to improve the interoperability and digitisation of biodiversity data. The project will also test out various technologies that are both affordable and adaptable to carry out species monitoring on a large scale. The end-to-end approach will be demonstrated via a number of science-based, policy-relevant use cases and via mechanisms to monitor, measure progress and drive community action towards increasing biodiversity data flows.

Within this remit, WP6 develops, implements and updates the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DC&E) Strategy and Plan for the Project, ensuring effective stakeholder engagement. It implements a series of campaigns to ensure outreach, participation and capacity building amongst key target audiences. The campaigns contribute to support the successful delivery of the project vision and its objectives by ensuring wide promotion of the project and its results to key target audiences via sound digital communications (website, social media presence, materials & digital marketing actions), presence at key events and networking (Campaign #1), building durable relationships with DTO data providers via onboarding mechanisms to increase sustained flows of biodiversity data via EMODnet Biology into the DTO (Campaign #2), promoting user uptake of DTO outputs with potential users, and ultimately strengthening knowledge exchange and professional relations amongst key stakeholder groups via the organisation and roll-out of workshops, networking and consultation activities, and building connections with international communities in support of the UN Decade of Ocean Science (Campaign #4).

WP6 is also concerned with creating impact, promoting the uptake and sustainable exploitation of project results beyond the consortium boundaries and the project-end in support of the [EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters](#).

The upcoming sections present the Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Strategy and Plan for DTO-BioFlow, structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** introduces the overall objectives for communication, dissemination and outreach, including a presentation of the key assets to be disseminated and the target stakeholder communities;
- **Chapter 3** explains how the campaign based approaches will be implemented. The activities foreseen in each of the campaigns are detailed and the expected performance results listed;
- **Chapter 4** focuses on DTO-BioFlow planned events & workshops, listing and describing, these with information on their purpose and expected audience;
- **Chapter 5** is dedicated to the exploitation measures that will be designed to ensure uptake of the DTO-BioFlow products.

2. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach Objectives

2.1. Objectives

The Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DC&E) Strategy for the DTO-Bioflow project has two major objectives:

- **Promote the DTO-BioFlow project by providing information and raising awareness about the project amongst diverse stakeholders through a dedicated communication campaign comprising a mix of communication activities, starting from the professional and considered project branding to website construction and content update, story-telling and social media outreach, will be planned and implemented to ensure high visibility for the project and its results, working with all Partners and their associated networks, and ensuring outreach to the wider public and policy stakeholders explaining the societal value of DTO-BioFlow;**
- **Maximise the engagement of key target audiences throughout the project and beyond** through three specific communication and outreach campaigns to be rolled-out during the project timeframe, each with a specific purpose and aligned with the key project action lines and expected outputs, namely: to onboard data providers, to showcase user uptake of DTO-BioFlow Outputs, and to support community building in support of the the Mission Ocean and the Ocean Decade.

Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DC&E) activities will be coordinated by Trust -IT within WP6 with contributions from all Partners with the ultimate objective of supporting knowledge awareness about key project activities, maximising exploitation of project outputs and creating impact beyond the project.

2.2. Key assets for dissemination

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CD&E) Strategy will focus on ensuring that the project's key assets are communicated widely, delivered to target stakeholders and their uptake monitored.

DTO-BioFlow will develop a range of assets that will be used both to inform and enable project implementation and as a resource for target users in the wider community. These include:

- **Inventory and analysis of biodiversity monitoring frameworks:** Publicly available report providing an overview and assessment of existing biodiversity monitoring frameworks in relation to needs, gaps, shortcomings and international efforts, including recommendations.
- **Prioritised inventory of unavailable data sources:** Publicly available inventory of unavailable data sources, ranked and prioritised for integration into the DTO infrastructure.
- **Assessment of the impact of missing data:** Publicly available report assessing the impact of missing data on the ability of digital solutions to represent reality and forecast future scenarios.
- **Barriers Playbook:** Publicly available report identifying and analysing barriers (impediments) to the access and use of biodiversity data in Europe and proposing scenarios to address these.
- **New sustained flows of biodiversity monitoring data available via DTO infrastructures, through:**

1. Open Calls to Data Holders (20 organisations via two calls)

2. Establishing digital connections to biodiversity monitoring networks as follows:

- Plankton and ARMs genomic observations networks
- Plankton imaging observation networks
- Fish, mammal and bird biologging networks
- Cetacean passive acoustic observation networks
- Additional data sources including from:
 - Citizen science
 - Official environmental reporting (MSFD, WISE, etc)
 - Marine industrial activities
 - Literature based data
 - Global sources not already covered by EU infrastructures
- **Increased FAIR biodiversity data and products:** available via EMODnet Biology and the EDITO infrastructure.
- **Demonstrator use cases:**
 - Essentially delivering the biodiversity component of the DTO, these policy relevant use cases will demonstrate the applicability of the digital replicas of real biodiversity systems to address environmental management and policy-relevant challenges. These use cases, to be developed by WP3, will demonstrate the end-to-end approach developed by DTO-BioFlow from new monitoring biodiversity data flows to potential application by end-users in the digital twin environments.
- **Validated and scalable new digital tools and services:**
 - New re-usable digital tools and services compatible and interoperable with, and scalable across, the different existing DTO infrastructures.
- **Data providers onboarding kit:** Publicly available capacity-building resource for biodiversity data providers to help them share their data in a FAIR way according to best practices.
- **New knowledge** on marine biodiversity monitoring, sustained data flows, and application in digital twin architectures, contributing to informing science and policy in key marine ecosystem challenge areas.
- **Strategic foresight report for increasing biodiversity data flows into DTO by 2030:** a policy-relevant horizon brief proposing SMART targets to increase the flow of biodiversity monitoring data into the DTO framework by 2030.

2.3. Target stakeholders

DTO-BioFlow stakeholders are considered in two broad categories: 1) “**Contributors**”, i.e., those who contribute to DTO-BioFlow, mainly in terms of data but also in terms of knowledge and participation to specific project activities; and 2) “**Users**”, i.e., those who will exploit DTO BioFlow outputs. Both categories are present in a range of stakeholder groups.

The figure below identifies which stakeholder groups (SG) will be targeted; what each will contribute to DTO-BioFlow; and what outputs they will use. There is substantial overlap between these groups and names listed are indicative/non-exhaustive. A more comprehensive mapping of stakeholders and target users will be developed and included in the next update of this report (M18).

Figure 1: DTO-BioFlow stakeholder groups

An initial list of important DTO BioFlow linkages with other projects/initiatives is provided in the table below, indicating their stakeholder group and relevance to the implementation of DTO-BioFlow activities. This list will be further developed and categorised by project partners as the project is developed in terms of their contribution to and/or uptake of DTO-BioFlow activities/outputs.

Table 1: Initial list of projects and initiatives that DTO-BioFlow will liaise with

Acronym	Full name	Framework	Stakeholder group	Link
MARCO-BOLO	MARine COastal BiODiversity Long-term Observations	Horizon Europe	Biodiversity research infrastructures	https://marcobolo-project.eu/
OBAMA-Next	Information products for marine biodiversity	Horizon Europe	Biodiversity research infrastructures	https://obama-next.eu
DiverSea	Integrated Observation, Mapping, Monitoring and Prediction for Functional Biodiversity of Coastal Seas	Horizon Europe	Biodiversity research infrastructures	https://www.ntnu.edu/diversea
EDITO Infra	EU public infrastructure of the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EDITO-Infra)	Mission Ocean Procurement	Digital Twin & EOSC Communities	https://edito-infra.eu/
EDITO Model Lab	Next generation of ocean numerical models to be integrated into EDITO-Infra	Mission Ocean call	Digital Twin & EOSC Communities	https://edito-modellab.eu/

Acronym	Full name	Framework	Stakeholder group	Link
DestinE	Destination Earth	ESA-ECMWF-EUMETSAT	Ocean Governance and Policy	https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/destination-earth
DITTO	UN Digital Twins of the Ocean	UN Ocean Decade program	Ocean Governance and Policy	https://ditto-oceandecade.org/
Iliad	Iliad - Digital Twins of the Ocean	European Green Deal	Digital Twin & EOSC Communities	https://ocean-twin.eu/
BioDT	Biodiversity Digital Twin for Advanced Modelling, Simulation and Prediction Capabilities	Horizon Europe	Digital Twin & EOSC communities	https://biодt.eu/
InterTwin	Interdisciplinary Digital Twin Engine (DTE)	Horizon-Europe - EOSC	Digital Twin & EOSC communities	https://www.intertwin.eu
GREAT	Green Deal Data Space	Digital Europe	Digital Twin & EOSC Communities	https://www.greatproject.eu
AD4GD	All Data 4 Green Deal	Horizon Europe	Digital Twin & EOSC Communities	https://ad4gd.eu/
ANERIS	operAtional seNsing life technologies for maRine ecosystemS	Horizon Europe	Biodiversity research infrastructures, Citizen Science	https://aneris.eu/
EMODnet Thematic Lots	European Marine Observation and Data Network	DG MARE	Biodiversity research infrastructures	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en
BioEcoOcean	Co-Creating Transformative Pathways to Biological and Ecosystem Ocean Observations	Horizon Europe	EU & Intl Ocean observing	https://www.uu.se/en/news/archive/2023-09-12-a-tool-to-increase-the-utility-of-ocean-observations
CLIMAREST	Ocean restore with biodiversity	Mission Ocean	EU & Intl Ocean observing	https://climarest.eu/
B-USEFUL	User-oriented Solutions for Improved Monitoring and Management of Biodiversity and Ecosystem services in vulnerable European Seas	Horizon Europe	Biodiveristy monitoring and Citizen Science	https://b-useful.eu/
FishGlob	FISH Biodiversity facing GLOBal Change	UN Ocean Decade project	Biodiversity-relevant ocean governance and policy	https://oceandecade.org/actions/fish-biodiversity-facing-

Acronym	Full name	Framework	Stakeholder group	Link
				global-change-fishglob/
Marbefes	MARine Biodiversity and Ecosystem Functioning leading to Ecosystem Services	Horizon Europe	Biodiversity research infrastructures; Ocean Governance Policy	https://marbefes.eu/
Blue-Cloud 2026	A Federated European FAIR and open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters	Horizon Europe - EOSC	Digital Twin & EOSC communities	https://blue-cloud.org/
AquaINFRA	FAIR Freshwater data with Pan-European Biodiversity case study	Horizon Europe - EOSC	Digital Twin & EOSC communities	https://aquainfra.eu/
AIRCENRE Networking Fridays	Atlantic International Research Centre	Dissemination Network	Citizen Science	https://www.aircentre.org/netfridays-marine-biodiversity-15/
EuroGOOS	European Global Ocean Observing System	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO	EU & Intl Ocean observing	https://eurogoos.eu/
EU4Ocean	The European Ocean Coalition	European Commission	Citizen Science (Ocean Literacy networks)	https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/theme/ocean-literacy-and-blue-skills/ocean-literacy/eu4ocean-coalition_en
eDNAqua-plan	Towards a European e-DNA library of marine and freshwater species	Horizon Europe	Biodiversity research; Mission Ocean	
DCO-Ocean Observing	Ocean Decade Coordination Office for Ocean Data Sharing	UNESCO Ocean Decade	Ocean Observing, Ocean governance and policy,	https://oceandecade.org/actions/decade-coordination-office-for-ocean-observing/
DCC Ocean Prediction	Ocean Decade Collaborative Centre for Ocean Prediction	UNESCO Ocean Decade	Ocean governance and policy,	https://oceandecade.org/actions/decade-collaborative-centre-for-ocean-prediction-dcc-op/
DCO-Ocean Data Sharing	Ocean Decade Coordination Office for Ocean Data Sharing	UNESCO Ocean Decade	Ocean governance and policy,	https://oceandecade.org/actions/decade-coordination-office-

Acronym	Full name	Framework	Stakeholder group	Link
			Biodiversity research infrastructures	for-ocean-data-sharing/

Media and multiplier channels

In addition to the systematic work to synergise and collaborate with projects and initiatives on specific matters, a list of media multipliers will also be exploited to ensure wide dissemination of the project press releases, announcements and social media posts. A non-exhaustive list of multipliers already identified and contacted for the launch of the DTO-BioFlow first open call is provided below. Project partners affiliated institutes are also considered as channels for further dissemination.

Table 2: Non-comprehensive list of multipliers

Who	Website	Twitter	Linkedin
EuroGOOS	https://eurogoos.eu/	@EuroGOOS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eurogoos/
JPI Oceans	https://www.jpi-oceans.eu/en/about	@jpioceans	https://www.linkedin.com/company/jpi-oceans/
National Biodiversity Future Centre	https://www.nbfc.it/	@nbfc_italy	
MARBEC - MARine Biodiversity Exploitation and Conservation	https://umr-marbec.fr/		https://www.linkedin.com/company/mfrc-atu/
Marine and Freshwater Research Centre (Ireland)	https://mfrc-atu.ie/		https://www.linkedin.com/company/mfrc-atu/
Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML)	https://www.pml.ac.uk/	@PlymouthMarine	https://www.linkedin.com/company/plymouth-marine-laboratory-&-pml-applications-ltd/
National Institute of Biology (NIB)	https://www.nib.si/eng/		https://www.linkedin.com/company/national-institute-of-biology/
European Marine Board IVZW	https://www.marineboard.eu/	@EMarineBoard	https://www.linkedin.com/company/european-marine-board/
Blue Marine Foundation	https://www.bluemarinesfoundation.com/	@Bluemarinesf	https://www.linkedin.com/company/blue-marine-foundation/
Centre of Marine Science	https://www.ccmr.ualg.pt/	@CienciasDoMar	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ccmar/
Marine Institute (IR)	https://www.marine.ie/	@MarineInst	https://www.linkedin.com/company/marine-institute/

Who	Website	Twitter	Linkedin
HAVSTOVAN: The Faroe Marine Research Institute	https://www.hav.fo/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=273&Itemid=265		
El Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO)			https://www.linkedin.com/company/ieo/
IFREMER	https://www.ifremer.fr/fr	@Ifremer_fr	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ifremer/
IOC UNESCO	https://www.ioc.unesco.org/en	@IocUnesco/ @OceanPractices	
Ocean Conservancy	https://oceanconservancy.org/about/	@OurOcean	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ocean-conservancy/
OGS	https://www.ogs.it/it	@OGS_IT	https://www.linkedin.com/company/istituto-nazionale-di-oceanografia-e-geofisica-sperimentale/
European Marine Research Centre Network	https://euomarinenetwork.eu/	@Euomarine_tw	https://www.linkedin.com/company/euomarine-network/

Both databases are maintained and updated as a collaborative effort by all project partners in the project shared repository on Sharepoint.

3. Dissemination & Communication Plan

3.1. DTO-Bioflow Campaigns

DTO-Bioflow CD&E Strategy is structured around four major campaigns, facilitating an agile implementation/assessment of activities across key target audiences. The four specialised campaigns will be carried out from M01 through M42. A campaign-based approach will bring benefits in terms of engagement of partners and external stakeholders, as well as impact, from constant monitoring and adjusting of the actions, to efficiency of the resources spent. Actions will be complemented by activities sustaining the project results exploitation and sustainability plan.

3.2. Campaign 1: DTO-Bioflow project communication

This campaign aims to ensure the project, its assets & results are communicated via its official channels with a consistent identity to all target stakeholders. The campaign will last the entire duration of the project and will seek to identify and connect with members of key target audiences for more targeted dissemination, exploitation and communication activities.

Activities included in this campaign will focus on highlighting the societal impact of the project while covering all the key action lines. The main messages that this campaign will deliver revolve around the following: *DTO-BioFlow will support delivery of Europe's biodiversity targets; it will unlock the potential of "sleeping" marine data; It will reorganise Europe's biodiversity data landscape and build the biodiversity digital component of the EU DTO. DTO- BioFlow can support biodiversity data collectors to make their data available via the DTO; DTO-BioFlow will enhance knowledge of biodiversity and how it is affected by human & environmental impacts.*

3.2.1. Project branding

In the proposal phase, the project's branding was carefully crafted, a pivotal element in establishing a cohesive visual identity and consolidating awareness among relevant communities.

A proposed logo (Figure X) underwent thorough discussions and garnered unanimous agreement from all partners to cover proper branding across the website, social media, and printed materials.

Figure 2: DTO-BioFlow logo

Beyond the logo, a suite of branded materials was created, including video conference background, presentation template, and a roll-up banner: these materials were successfully deployed during the project's kick off meeting ensuring a consistent and impactful presentation of our brand. This also has the effect to create a sense of pride and community amongst the partners.

Figure 3: Branded materials ready by kick-off meeting

A poster and a corresponding flyer, as well as stickers, were created as additional branding materials. These features will take centre stage in upcoming dissemination events, solidifying our project's visual identity even further.

3.2.2. Public website

The DTO-BioFlow website is hosted at dto-bioflow.eu and acts as the main showcase for all project results and information, thematically arranged.

To provide the best results, a structured process is followed by the DTO-BioFlow WP6 lead organisation Trust-IT Srl and affiliated entity COMMpla Srl (Figure X). The marketing team created an initial draft of the website structure and design based on the primary project goals and UX concepts. The graphic team uses their knowledge to create a visually appealing mockup, while the technical team participates in the latter implementation and testing phases, after which the process is returned to the marketing team for input. When necessary, the FIGMA platform is used for mock-up phases to improve team engagement.

Figure 4: DTO-BioFlow website development process

Figure 5: DTO-BioFlow website development process on Figma

The DTO-BioFlow website was unveiled with the official launch of the project and is set to undergo significant expansion in the coming months, encompassing all essential sections to provide a comprehensive and user-friendly platform. Up to now the following sections have been added:

- ‘About’ page, with introduction to the partners and work plan of the project;
- ‘Events’ page and ‘News’ page;
- A dedicated page for the Open Call for marine biodiversity (monitoring) data and relative webform for the submission of the application

3.2.3. Social Media

Social media channels play a central role in the public communication activities for DTO-BioFlow, reaching out well beyond professionals and researchers, relevant profiles and actors in the ecosystem. Marine Biodiversity is a topic of conversation also in terms of social interest and the project will exploit relevant opportunities across a range of channels.

DTO-BioFlow uses the following social media channels: Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube, all characterised by the coordinated branding.

Figure 6: Social media headers of DTO-BioFlow profiles

The DTO-BioFlow project's social media platforms have seen constant involvement since the initial Kick-off Meeting on September 27-28, with a substantial rise in followers over the last three months. At the time of writing, the existing social media community is captured in Table X. We will increase our current network of multipliers across the various target communities. By the end of the project, we want to have gained between 3000 and 5000 joint followers

Channel	Link	Followers as of M3
Twitter	twitter.com/DTOBioFlow	99
LinkedIn	linkedin.com/company/dto-bio-flow	275
YouTube	youtube.com/@DTOBioFlowProject	9

3.2.4. Videos

Videos are an important tool to provide highly engaging content, and make it easier for those who do not want (or do not have the time) to read through complex material to get a better understanding of the project. The DTO-BioFlow YouTube channel serves as the primary repository for all video content created within the project, encompassing interviews, promotional videos, and webinar recordings.

The first series of videos crafted for DTO-BioFlow comprises interviews with the coordinator and each work package (WP) lead, filmed during the Kick-off meeting. Each WP lead introduced the role of their institution within the project and described the work plan that he/she will coordinate. Each video is expected to reach

at least 300 organic views across platforms as of the end of the project. Background footage of the meeting, including the coordinator’s facilities and biodiversity monitoring instrumentation demonstrated by experts, was also taken for use in future films.

Figure 7: Frame from the DTO-BioFlow Kick-off meeting video

Three more videos will be shot during the duration of the project with the aim to raise awareness about marine biodiversity and the importance of the availability of marine biodiversity data, encouraging new data providers, including citizen scientists and biodiversity enthusiasts to engage with the DTO-Bioflow project and explaining the societal relevance of DTO-BioFlow.

3.2.5. Newsletters

A newsletter template was designed in line with the project branding, debuting with the first official DTO-BioFlow newsletter issued on 7 November 2023, after the launch of the first Open Call. By the end of the project we plan to produce up to 18 newsletters.

Figure 8: The first issue of the DTO-BioFlow newsletter

The DTO-BioFlow newsletter will feature the main news, upcoming events, and other highlights from the project and its wider ecosystem, serving as a key channel for reaching out to already interested contacts who decided to sign up. Newsletters are sent via Mailjet and at the time of writing this deliverable we had reached out to more than 100 subscribers.

3.2.6. Promotional & Dissemination Materials

More promotional and dissemination materials are envisioned over the course of DTO-BioFlow, supporting outreach activities as well as participation in third party events.

The first DTO-BioFlow poster was designed for and presented at the EMODnet Conference which took place on 29 and 30 of November 2023 in Brussels and online. (<https://dto-bioflow.eu/news/emodnet-open-conference-2023-highlights-dto-bioflow-contribution-eu-dtos-biodiversity-mission>) For the same occasion stickers and flyers were produced.

Figure 9: Branded materials

3.2.7. Press Releases

DTO-BioFlow will also exploit press releases as means to disseminate newsworthy project results or events to engage relevant media and publishers in both the marine research and open science communities. The **first DTO BioFlow press release** was published on **29 September 2023** after the kick-off meeting, and **the second one** was published on **31 October** after the launch of the Open Call, with all Partners actively encouraged to share widely. Both press releases have also been distributed to relevant organisations and initiatives, achieving publication on several relevant channels, a selection can be found below.

The project will produce press releases on a case by case, with an indicative number of a total of 4 press releases by the end of the project.

Table 3: Some of the press clippings & back links resulting from the first DTO-BioFlow press release

#	Channel	Community	Link
1	Géant	National research and education networks	https://connect.geant.org/2023/10/24/building-the-biodiversity-component-of-the-digital-twin-of-the-ocean-dto-bioflow-horizon-europe-project-kicked-off
2	ECO Magazine	Marine Science	https://www.ecomagazine.com/news/research/building-the-biodiversity-component-of-the-digital-twin-of-the-ocean
4	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)	Research & Academia	https://www.vlaanderen.be/inbo/en-GB/projects/dto-bioflow-integration-of-biodiversity-monitoring-data-into-the-digital-twin-ocean
5	Naturalis	Research	https://www.naturalis.nl/integration-of-biodiversity-monitoring-data-into-digital-twin-ocean-dto-bioflow
6	Sintef	Research	https://www.sintef.no/en/projects/2023/dto-bioflow/
7	LifeWatch ERIC	European research Infrastructure	https://www.lifewatch.eu/dto-bioflow/
8	Seascope Belgium	Research	https://www.seascopebelgium.be/news/seascope-belgium-joins-kick-meeting-dto-bioflow-project

Table 4: Some of the press clippings resulting from the press release announcing the open call

#	Channel	Community	Link
1	Science Magazine	Press & Media	https://scienmag.com/tag/biodiversity/
2	Bioengineer.org	Press & Media	https://bioengineer.org/building-the-digital-replica-of-our-seas-an-open-call-for-crucial-biodiversity-data-to-restore-ocean-ecosystems/
3	Europa Innovazione	Eu Project information network	https://www.europainnovazione.com/dto-bioflow-pubblicato-il-bando-per-la-conservazione-delloceano-tramite-dati-sulla-biodiversita/
4	FIRST (Finanziamenti per l'Innovazione, Ricerca e Sviluppo)	Eu Project information network	https://first.art-er.it/news/horizon-europe-call-tutela-dellecosistema-marino
5	Nano Alumni Network for the Ocean	Research&Academia	https://nf-pogo-alumni.org/opportunities/jobs-funding/24112023-4/
6	Swedish Biodiversity data Infrastructure	Research	https://biodiversitydata.se/news/call-for-marine-data/
7	EMODnet	Research	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/dto-bioflow-open-call-help-unlock-sustained-and-long-term-marine-biodiversity-data-and-foster
8	EuroMarine Science Network	Research & Academia	https://euromarinenetwork.eu/news/open-call-for-marine-biodiversity-data-holders-dto-bioflow/
9	MarcoBolo	European Project	https://marcobolo-project.eu/contribute-to-marine-biodiversity-research-with-marco-bolo/
10	OBIS	UNESCO	https://obis.org/2023/12/07/dto-bioflow-call/
11	Springer Nature	Research & Academia	https://communities.springernature.com/posts/building-the-digital-replica-of-our-seas-an-open-call-for-crucial-biodiversity-data-to-restore-ocean-ecosystems
12	GenCat.cat	Press & Media	https://exteriors.gencat.cat/ca/ambits-dactuacio/afers_exteriors/ue/fons_europeus/detalls/noticia/20231106_dto-bio-flow

3.2.8. Campaign KPIs

Indicator	Measure	Expected Value	
		By M18	by M42
Website	# session/month	>1k	3k
Social Media	# of followers across all platforms	3k	5k
Videos	# of views for each video	300	1500
Newsletter	# of newsletters published	4	18
Press release	# of press releases launched	1	4

3.3. Campaign 2 - Biodiversity Providers Onboarding Campaign

This second campaign will compile and orchestrate a series of activities with the purpose to onboard new providers of biodiversity data for the DTO and raise awareness of what the formats, standards, and practices necessary for making data usable by the DTO. The target stakeholders are data providers from Ocean governance and policy (SG#1), Biodiversity marine data services and research infrastructures (SG#2), Mission Lighthouses and Blue Parks (SG#3), Research and Academia (SG#4), EU and International Organisations (SG#5), Blue-Economy networks (SG#6) & Civil Society (SG#7).

A sample of the main messages to convey are: *DTO-BioFlow resources can enable you/your organisation to make your biodiversity data FAIR, available via EMODnet and useable by the DTO helping EU to deliver on its 2030 biodiversity targets; DTO-BioFlow provides grants & training for data users to support them in making their biodiversity data FAIR and usable by the EU DTO.*

3.3.1. Visibility and Promotion of DTO-Bioflow open calls for data holders

The provision of support to the launch and set-up of the open calls for data holders is at the core of this campaign, including their promotion across the relevant networks, the support to the applicants, the provision of all necessary information as well as a transparent and fair application and evaluation process. This activity will be run in close collaboration with WP2 - *Task 2.5 "Organise open calls to data holders"*.

The communication and technical management of the open calls will be performed via the project website. At the time of writing this deliverable, the webpage of the first open call for marine biodiversity data is published at the link <https://dto-bioflow.eu/marine-biodiversity-data-open-call> accessible from the main menu. It provides interested applicants with all the relevant information about who can apply, funding and eligibility criteria, and the assessment process. The open call webform is also available online for registered users and finally, a support service is provided via the contact mailing list opencalls@dto-bioflow.eu.

Figure 10 : preview of the Open Call page and application form

All open calls will be published via the DTO-BioFlow website and disseminated widely. The selected applicants will be publicly announced via the DTO-BioFlow website within 30 days of the evaluations being carried out and will include a description of selected applications, i.e. the project (dataset) title, and the organisation and country of the successful applicants.

DTO-BioFlow first Open Call details

Published officially on Tuesday, October 31st, this single-stage call will remain open for applications until January 17th at 17:00 CET. This grant is open to a wide range of marine biodiversity data holders, including European networks, citizen science organisations, research institutes, universities, and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) who can facilitate sustained and long-term ingestion of previously inaccessible data into the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO).

The evaluation process is scheduled to occur from January 18th to February 8th, 2024. Eligible proposals will be selected based on multiple criteria, including their relevance, potential impact, ability to sustain data flow and automate processes, uniqueness, and overall proposal quality.

Each third party can access a maximum funding amount of 60,000 EUR. This funding will be distributed in two payments, with half awarded at the start of the project and the other half awarded upon successful completion of the proposed activities.

Visibility to the open call was provided via a dedicated announcement and press release, which at the time of writing is being distributed to a list of relevant media contacts and partner networks (see par. 3.2.7 Press Releases), as well as via continuous social media campaigns. At the time of writing the open call press release was published and distributed across 30+ channels and networks including the EurekAlert publisher channel, offering news releases visibility to more than 14,000 reporters and freelancers from 90+ countries, as a news release at <https://www.eurekalert.org/news-releases/1009555>.

A second call is expected to be launched by 2025.

Figure 11: preview of the Open call press release on EurekAlert

3.3.2. Data Provider onboarding kit

Online, digital materials providing entry-level information on who's who in the biodiversity data landscape, existing data providers, FAQs, and links to the inventory of data sources (WP2) feeding into DTO will be made available from the DTO-BioFlow public website. The onboarding kit will feature key elements such as training guidelines, best practices on how to make data "DTO Compatible", i.e. FAIR and properly formatted to be submitted to EMODnet, (meta)standards to follow, repositories to use etc. The kit will be shared with relevant projects/initiatives, including ESFRI, to help identify workflows, observation activities (public, research & blue economy), and citizen science initiatives that could feed into the DTO. The kit will start to be available from month 8, for the 1st Data Grants Holders Workshop, and it will be updated if necessary for the 2nd Data Grants Holders Workshop. The material of the onboarding kit will be available online in the DTO website.

3.3.3. DTO-Bioflow training guidelines

A series of online training materials will be developed, i.e., guidelines on how to make data "DTO Compatible", factsheets, based on available resources and existing materials as well as outputs from WP2 Data Holders workshops and identified data gaps from the use cases in WP3 and the demonstrators in WP4. Guidelines for the standardisation and harmonisation of data production and exchange will cover data deriving from different biodiversity observation networks and will act as an open best practices recommendation to complement the flow of data in the DTO. The guidelines will be available online for all interested parties and stakeholders and they will be included in the data provider onboarding kit (3.3.2). The material of the FAIR Training Course (<https://www.vliz.be/en/embrc-fair-training-course>), organised in the beginning of 2024 by EMBRC and designed by VLIZ and UGent, can be used as a basis for the formulation of the DTO-Bioflow training guidelines.

3.3.4. Campaign KPIs

Indicator	Measure	Expected Value	
		By M18	by M42
Open calls applications	# of projects selected**	Min 8 max 10**	Min 16 and max 20**
Data provider onboarding kit	# of items available in the kit	>10	>50
Training guidelines	# Total downloads on Zenodo	200	800

** The total budget available for the 2 open calls is 1.000.000€, so each call has an indicative budget around 500.000€. Considering a maximum amount of 60.000€ allocated per successful project, the number of overall projects selected for funding will vary between 16 and 20, according to the requested budget.

3.4. Campaign 3 - User uptake of DTO Outputs

This campaign is dedicated to promote uptake of DTO-BioFlow FAIR data, products, digital tools & services, including the DTO-BioFlow Use Cases and their outputs with potential users (intermediate and end). Target stakeholders of the activities planned under this campaign are users of FAIR biodiversity relevant data and products from all stakeholder groups.

Sample main messages to deliver include: *Stakeholders have access to increased scale & resolution of FAIR biodiversity relevant data & products via EMODnet and the DTO; DTO developers can test the functioning of their environments with new DTO-BioFlow unlocked data streams in real life applications; Stakeholders working in relevant areas have access to DUC and/or to their outputs.*

3.4.1. Biodiversity DTO User stories

Digital user stories will be produced in collaboration with WP3 and WP4 as downloadable best practices to describe use cases, applications and demonstrators as examples for further uptake by similar communities. They will include details useful for further exploitation of the models and data products (e.g., owners, TRL, replicability, costs).

3.4.2. Workshops and events

Uptake of DTO-BioFlow FAIR data, products, digital tools & services will be boosted via the organisation of a series of workshops and events, in presence and online. They include matchmaking online events, users' workshops with DTO developers, intermediate users of the demonstrator use cases to address the technical aspects of migration to the DTO; performance review workshops to design and plan the dissemination of the digital tools. A complete list of the planned events is included in Chapter 5.

3.4.3. Campaign KPIs

Indicator	Measure	Expected Value	
		By M18	by M42
Biodiversity DTO User stories	# of stories produced	n.a.	10

3.5. Campaign 4: International community building in support of the Mission & UN Decade of Ocean Science

A fourth campaign will be orchestrated to ensure that a community of relevant international stakeholders across all stakeholder groups is engaged to exchange best practice, build capacity, define targets and commitments to increase flow of biodiversity data into the DTO by 2030.

DTO Bioflow will contact relevant initiatives in the European and international biodiversity and DTO community, including the UN Decade of Ocean Science programs, to implement technical and outreach collaboration. These will include DITTO and its working groups, OceanPredict, Coast Predict and appropriate Decade Collaborative centres, GOOS and related global projects (e.g., AtlantOS, ICOS, MBON, OneARGO), data infrastructures (eg. IODE, ODIS, Ocean Decade Data Coordination Platform) and Horizon Europe projects (MARCO-BOLO, B-USEFUL and BioOcean5D projects). DTO-Bioflow also aims to provide specific input, guidance and recommendations towards policy measures concerning the digital solutions required for the Mission, aligning with wider developments (EU Green Deal Data Space) and more specifically the EU DTO. DTO-Bioflow partners will also liaise with key EU Mission Lighthouses & Blue Parks initiatives and UN Decade of Ocean Science programmes for further exploitation of results.

One Ocean Decade workshop will be organised in Month 36 to engage with international DTO communities and relevant programmes of the UN Decade of Ocean Science. Policy recommendations building also on work across all WPs, will be collected into an “Horizon Brief”, proposing SMART targets to increase the flow of biodiversity data into the DTO framework by 2030.

The policy recommendations and outcomes from the project will be presented during a final conference to “pitch” project results to policy stakeholders, promote relevant conclusions and recommendations towards increasing the flow of biodiversity monitoring data into the DTO framework by 2030.

3.5.1. Campaign KPIs

Indicator	Measure	Expected Value	
		By M18	by M42
DTO & Ocean Decade collaborations	# of Collaborations established	2	10
International workshop	# of participants	n.a.	100
Final conference	# of participants	n.a.	300

4. DTO-BioFlow Events & Workshops

4.1 DTO-BioFlow events

To better connect with the different DTO-BioFlow audiences, a series of target events will be organised in the course of the project with clear objectives, stakeholder audience and expected outputs in mind. Each event will have dedicated pre-event organisational support (agenda set-up, engagement of the speakers, event web pages including registration procedure), support for its promotion across target stakeholders (ensuring social media visibility, Direct Email Marketing and press campaigns); live support during the event and live social media posting; and after the event follow-up ensuring coordination of post-event reporting and publication and promotion of the event proceedings and other materials.

The organisation of DTO-BioFlow’s different series of events is highly dependent on the needs of the different project work packages (WPs). These events will support WPs in delivering their results. DTO-BioFlow communication team will customise the branding for each series of events, for stronger impact and “brand memory”. Furthermore, the organisation of these events will extend DTO-BioFlow’s current network. These events may be organised as stand-alone events by DTO-BioFlow or also combined, when appropriate, with events organised by other initiatives to maximise effort and impact.

Table 5: Overview of DTO-BioFlow events to be organised

What	Milestone / deliverable	Goal	Stakeholders	Tentative timeframe & KPIs
Workshop w/ monitoring network (WP3 & WP4)	Milestone 5	Workshop with data monitoring networks to assess potential new data flows against the needs of the Demonstrator Use Cases to address marine ecosystem challenges.	Marine Data Services & Research Infrastructures; Ocean Governance & Policy	October 2023 KPI: 1 workshop organised
Workshops to build data Flows (WP5 - in support of WP2, WP3, WP4)	Milestone 13	Online workshops organised with sensor networks, data providers, HPC stakeholders to design, test and assess the models and products developed - Supporting operationalized data streams & demonstrators by digital tools & services to support WP2, WP3 and WP4 and biodiversity data providers to accelerate data processing workflows.	Marine Data Services & Research Infrastructures; Ocean Observing; Blue Economy Networks	December 2024, December 2025 & December 2026 KPI: 50 workshop participants aggregated per year - perhaps in synergy with related workshops

What	Milestone / deliverable	Goal	Stakeholders	Tentative timeframe & KPIs
Data Grants Workshops (WP2 & WP3)	Milestones 21, 22	Physical workshops to train the Open calls selected data holders on how to properly submit their data	Marine Data Services & Research Infrastructure; Research & Academia; Blue Economy Networks; Civil Society	April 2024 & March 2025 KPI: 8 participants each workshop
Matchmaking online events (WP6)	Milestone 25	Virtual, moderated and guided with paired DTO-BioFlow experts and potential users to promote uptake and application of DTO-BioFlow generated data and digital outputs	Marine Data Services & Research Infrastructures; Research & Academia; Ocean Observing; Blue Economy Networks; Digital Twin & EO SC Communities	December 2024, August 2025, February 2026, August 2026. KPI: 40 participants each workshop
Users Stories Webinars (WP6 & WP4)	–	Workshops with DTO developers, intermediate users of the demonstrator use cases, to address the technical aspects of migration to the DTO and facilitate their implementation in the DTO	Marine Data Services & Research Infrastructure; Research & Academia; Blue Economy Networks; Civil Society	October 2025, December 2025, February 2026 & April 2026 KPI: 20 participants each workshop
DUC performance review Workshops (WP4)	Milestone 14	Workshops with DTO developers and WP4 & WP5 experts to review the performance of the DUC on the DTO infrastructure to document and fill the remaining data, model, algorithm, and service gaps necessary to achieve an end to-end approach	Marine Data Services & Research Infrastructure; Mission Lighthouses & BlueParks; Ocean Observing	January 2026 KPI: 20 participants each workshop
DUC model outputs design & dissemination	Milestone 15	Workshop with DTO developers, and relevant project experts/stakeholders to	Research & Academia; Ocean Observing; Blue	May 2026

What	Milestone / deliverable	Goal	Stakeholders	Tentative timeframe & KPIs
Workshop (WP4)		design and plan the dissemination of the digital tools and services, DUC, and their outputs to relevant end-users, including the ecological narratives and associated training materials for non-specialist users	Economy Networks.	KPI: 20 participants each workshop
Ocean Decade International Workshop (WP6)	Milestone 23	To engage with international DTO communities & relevant programmes of the UN Decade of Ocean Science	Ocean Governance & Policy; Blue Economy Networks; Civil Society; Digital Twin & EOOSC Communities	August 2026 KPI: 100 participants
Horizon Brief Expert Meetings (WP6)	Milestone 26	Expert workshops synthesising findings into “Horizon Brief”, proposing SMART targets to increase the flow of biodiversity data into the DTO framework by 2030	All stakeholders	December 2024, October 2025 & June 2026 KPI: 8-10 participants each workshop
Final conference & exploitation exhibition	Milestones 24	Pitch project results to policy stakeholders, promote relevant conclusions and recommendations towards increasing the flow of biodiversity monitoring data into the DTO framework by 2030	All stakeholders	July 2026 KPI: 300 participants

4.2 Third-party events

DTO-BioFlow partners will actively participate in relevant third party events as speakers, organising sessions or workshops, presenting posters or giving talks (KPI:40 events). Presence at these events will allow:

- The promotion of DTO-BioFlow work to different target stakeholders;
- Collection of new contacts for database enrichment opportunities;
- Direct engagement with potential DTO-BioFlow audiences;
- Identification of win-win synergies with different organisations and initiatives, for potential collaboration and knowledge transfer;

- Dissemination of scientific results and engagement with the scientific community.

A non-exhaustive list of the events identified as relevant for 2024 is provided in the table below. The aim is to reach events in different locations and to a wider/more diverse audience, since the project will have a higher number of results to be showcased. As described in the previous chapters, DTO-BioFlow will organise its own events to reach target audiences that may not be heavily represented in the events indicated below.

Table 6 Potential events to showcase DTO-BioFlow

Event	Location	Audience
Oceanology International March 2024	United Kingdom	Businesses, academics and government
EGU24 April 2024	Austria	Geoscientists from all over the world at a meeting covering all disciplines of the Earth, planetary, and space sciences
OCEANS 2024 April 2024	Singapore	Global maritime professionals
UN Ocean Decade Conference April 2024	Spain	Governments, leaders, maritime sectors, philanthropy, universities, private sector, NGOs
IMDIS May 2024	Norway	Stakeholders working in the fields of information technology, marine data management, research, environmental protection
European Maritime Day May 2024	Denmark	Members of the European Commission and high-level representatives of the member states and the European regions, the maritime economy, business associations and other stakeholders
TNC2024 June 2024	France	Research and education community
EOSC Symposium October 2024	Germany	Policy and decision makers, experts and practitioners from the EOSC fields

5. Exploitation measures

A project exploitation and sustainability plan (D1.5) will be produced detailing how the established data flows and demonstrators will continue to function after the project ends, as part of EMODnet Biology as well as via the DTO infrastructure and applications. Trust-IT (WP6) and VLIZ (WP1) will work with WP and Task Leads to produce individual and joint exploitation plans for the structured flows of data into the DTO (WP3), the use cases and applications (WP4), the digital tools & services (WP5) and policy outputs (WP6), taking into consideration current and potential new users, defining a value proposition to each user segment and addressing relevant IPR management aspects. The plan will specify performance indicators to measure the success of the project towards achievable targets regarding increasing biodiversity data flows into the DTO by 2030, detailing also technical and/or operational requirements and resources needed for wider exploitation at an operational level.

Key Exploitable Result templates will be provided and maintained across the WP3 and WP4 demonstrators, as part of user stories created (see Campaign #3) and identify scenarios for further exploitation of the use cases. The plan will also identify recommendations to be fed into the Horizon Brief policy document (Campaign #4).

The data products that will be produced by the DTO-BioFlow project will mostly be made available via EMODnet Biology and within the DTO data lake. The new data made available to EMODnet Biology via the European Ocean Biodiversity Information System (EurOBIS) data backbone, will also flow to the global Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF).

WP6 will disseminate the final DTO-BioFlow exploitation and sustainability plan (D1.11) to key stakeholders and will make available relevant, public information via the project public website.

The final conference will also be a moment where to clarify exploitation opportunities and open a discussion with the target stakeholder about sustainability mechanisms.

6. Measuring Impact & Monitoring

Evaluation of the Dissemination and Communication activities will be based on several points. KPIs are tracked on a monthly basis monitoring the dissemination, communication, papers submission and presence/organisation at events. Five monitoring trackers have been built based on the reporting forms available on the EC funding and tenders portal entry point for participants in funded projects (see Table 7). By using them as a benchmark, it will smooth the reporting process and ensure that the communication and dissemination activities are properly reported. Instructions about how to track the activities have already been shared with DTO-BioFlow partners.

Table 7 DTO-BioFlow list of Monitoring and Assessment trackers

Tracker	Description
Publications	Papers, articles and other publications published by DTO-BioFlow consortium partners
Dissemination Activities	Performed activities to reach target audiences, that is, any potential user of the project results. These activities can be: Clustering Activities, Collaboration with EU-funded projects, Conference, Education and Training Events, Meetings, Other Scientific Collaboration, Other Scientific Cooperation, Other
Communication Activities	Performed activities to reach a wide audience, that is, not just aimed to reach potential end-users, but the general audience, including media and general public. The aim is to promote the project in general and its value-added and not just the project results. Examples of some communication activities are visual identity (e.g. logo), public website, flyers, social media, videos, press releases, etc
Events	Events organised under DTO-BioFlow and also all third-party events (events not organised by PREPSOIL) where DTO-BioFlow had visibility (e.g. poster, exhibition stand, lightning talk, panel discussion, presentation, paper submission etc)
KPIs	General KPIs related to communication and dissemination activities

7. Conclusions

This document describes the “Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DC&E) Strategy and Plan” of DTO-BioFlow, as part of “WP6 - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation” and aims to orchestrate a series of dissemination, exploitation, and communication actions organised around four different engagement campaigns to ensure the DTO-BioFlow objectives and impacts are achieved.

This document is agreed upon with all the DTO-BioFlow WP6 partners and constitutes a plan to deliver a series of activities to which all partners, according to the effort indicated in the DTO-BioFlow work plan, commit to contribute.

The plan covers the period from M3 (November 2023) to M18 (February 2025), when an updated version is scheduled as D36 (D6.2). This new release will report all the activities performed between M1 and M18 and will plan from M19 through M42.